

1-TOM, 12-SON
THE APPLICATION OF ARTICLES, AS WELL AS ISSUES AND
SOLUTIONS AROUND THEIR USAGE

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek

The Faculty of Psychology, the department of Foreign languages
Philology and foreign languages

Scientific advisor: Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi
nafisateshaboyeva@gmail.com

Student of group 203-20: Abdurozikova I.I.

E-mail : ismigulbegim@gmail.com

Abstract: This article is about a/an article and its usage. This article also discusses one and ones.

Key words: a article, an article, usages, one and ones

INTRODUCTION

Many international certifications also test writing skills. Requiring them to load effectively to reach help through that eye. Effective loading of the above articles will help the student to score higher than the above qualification. On the other hand, articles are significantly more problematic. however, the ability to know articles, to know a/an articles, to analyze them correctly, to work with nouns will analyze such a result. Therefore, in this article, you will find an analysis of necessary and interesting information about a/n articles, its use, one and ones.

I. MATERIALS

An article is usually used before a noun. Articles are divided into 2 types. 1) a/ an indefinite article

2) the definite article.

A and an article are only used before singular countable nouns. An article is used before a singular noun that begins with a consonant. An article is used before a singular noun that begins with a vowel. A/an article is not used before plural or uncountable nouns.

Usages.

1. When we first talk about a person or thing in general, the articles a and an are used. However, the-articiple is used when we give additional information about that person or thing.

Example:

1) I bought a new car yesterday.

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It is black.

2) I have been reading a book for a week.

The book is about friendship.

2. Indefinite articles are used before professions.

Example:

1) Tom works as a teacher at school.

2) Ann is a doctor.

However, indefinite articles are not used before occupations after verbs such as appoint, elect, choose, become, make.

Example:

1) They have appointed him director of company

2) He was elected chairman last week.

3. Indefinite articles are used when describing what something is.

This / that / itis a/an singular noun

Example:

1) This is a book

2) That is a car

3) It is London

4. Indefinite articles are used in the meanings of existence and possession.

There is/ have (got) + a/an singular noun

1. There is a newspaper on the table

2. I have got a modern big house

but where? the-article is used in the meaning. Because in this case, what is being sought is clear to both the listener and the speaker.

Where is / are + The

Example:

Where is the money?

Where are the children?

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5. In general, the article is not used before people's names.

Example :

- 1) Tom,
- 2) Anna,
- 3) Mr. Johns

A/An + name

A+ Mr/Mrs/ Ms/ Miss/ Dr.....name

But when talking about a stranger, the indefinite article is used before the name.

Example :

- 1) A mr Johns called you
- 2) That letter was send A Ann

6. In the sense of a work created by a person, a picture, a book, a painting, the indefinite article is used before nouns to form the meaning of metonymy.

Example :

- 1) I am reading an Agatha Christie these days
- 2) There is a Picasso on the wall.

7. Indefinite articles are not used before parts of food.

Example:

- 1.breakfast 2.lunch 3.dinner 4.supper 5.tea

However, if the quality comes before the parts of the food, the articles a/an are used.

a/an adjective + breakfast ,lunch,dinner,supper, tea

Example :

1. A big breakfast
2. A cooked lunch
3. A delicious dinner

8. Articles are usually not used before illnesses.

Example :

1. Diabetes

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2. Bronchitis
3. Meningitis
4. Rabies
5. Influenza

But with the following diseases, the article can be used or not:

A headache ,A sorethroat, A cold ,A Cough, A Temperature
The flu The measles , The mumps

9. Indefinite article is used before nouns of time, weight and quantity.

In this case, "per" is considered a synonym for a/an.

Example :

1. an/per hour
2. a/per day
3. a/per month
4. a/per year
5. a/per kilo
6. a /per litre

10. The indefinite article is used before the following words:

1. A dozen= one dozen
2. A hundred=one hundred
3. A thousand =one thousand
4. A million=one million
5. A billion=one billion

11. The indefinite article is used the following words:

what ,such, quite, rather

what ,such, quite, rather +a/an adjective singular noun

Example:

1. What a beautiful day!
2. What a pity!

12. The indefinite article is used with a/an adjective one

Example:

I would like to buy a shirt
I need a black one

ONE & ONES

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Usage :

1. One is used to emphasize number.

Example :

- 1) I have got one car, but he has got two
- 2) One of my brothers is a student

2. One is used to express the past tense.

Example:

- 1) One day
- 2) One morning
- 3) One afternoon
- 4) One evening/night
- 5) One summer/ winter
- 6) One September/October
- 7) One moment/ time

3. one is used instead of a singular noun, and ones is used instead of a plural noun.

Example :

- 1) There are three cars here: a red one, a black one and a white one.
- 2) -Which bag is yours?
-The black one.

II. RESULT AND CONCLUSION

Finally, we come to the conclusion that articles play an important role in our speech. Because the noun group that is actively used in our oral speech, in turn, requires taking articles. However, due to the existence of indefinite articles, definite articles, and cases of non-use of articles in both oral and written speech processes, the widespread use of articles causes certain inconveniences to the reader. and then, so it is desirable to pay attention to the skill of improving the level of knowledge of articles. Each article has its own characteristics, so students are advised to consider the above points and refer to the examples given for the rules of each article.

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